

VIRUSLI GEPATIT B KASALLIDA KO’RILADIGAN EPIDEMIOLOGIK VA PROFILAKTIK CHORA TADBIRLAR

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Mavzuning dolzarbligi: Virusli gepatit B kasalligi (VGB)– surunkali va ba’zan o’tkir kechuvchi kasallik hisoblanib, ushbu kasallikni Gepadnoviruslar keltirib chiqaradi Bu kasallik yengil shakldan tortib, o’lim bilan tugaydigan va og’ir asoratlanadigan keng tarqalgan kasallikdir

Ishning maqsadi: VGB kasalligini oldini olishga qaratilgan profilaktika chora tadbirlarini amalga oshirish. Aholi orasida sanitar epidemiologik nazoratni taminlash

Material va metodlar: Kasallanganlar orasida o’tkir surunkali va tashuvchilarni operativ va retrospektiv usulda aniqlash

Tadqiqot natijalari: Virusli gepatit B (VGB) - Surunkali, ba’zida o’tkir kechadigan yuqumli kasallik bo’lib, kasallikni gepadnavirus (Hepadnavirus) keltirib DNK saqlovchi virus. Manbai VGB ni surunkali kechirayotgan bemorlar , surunkali tashuvchilar va yaqqol klinik belgilari bilan kechayotgan o’tkir shakldagi bemorlar. Yuqish mexanizmi parenteral yo’l orqali yuqadi. Moyilligi parenteral yuqqanligi sababli VGB turli yoshdagilar kasallanishi mumkin. Ularni tarkibini asosan narkotik modda qabul qiluvchilar, tibbiy muolaja oluvchilar va umumiy kosmetologik anjomlardan foydalanuvchilar tashkil qiladi. Mavsumiyligi mavjud emas, lekin kasallik kuz-qish-bahorda ko’proq uchraydi. Kasallikning tarqalganligi O’zbekistonda kasallanishning rasmiy qayd qilinishi yo’lga qo’yilgan 1970 yillardan boshlab to 1995 yillargacha kasallanish ko’rsatkichining oshib borganligi kuzatiladi. 2000 yillardan boshlab ushbu kasallikka qarshi rejali emlash kiritilishi natijasida kasallanish ko’rsatkichining tobora kamayib borayotganligi aniqlandi Respublikamizda keyingi tashuvchilar soni birmuncha ko’payganligi qayd qilinadi. Profilaktik chora tadbirlar maxsus va maxsus bo’lmagan chora tadbirlar mavjud .Maxsus emlash reja asosida va epidemiologik ko’rsatmaga asosan amalga oshiriladi. Hozirgi vaqtda O’zbekistonda

endjeriks– B (Belgiya), “Virion“ (Tomsk, Rossiya) vaksinalaridan foydalaniladi. Emlash 3 marotaba amalga oshiriladi: Bola tug’ilgan kuni 24 soat ichida, 2 oyligida va 6 oyligida. VGB vaksinasidan zudlik bilan qilinadigan profilaktika 4 bosqichda amalga oshiriladi: dastlabki kuni, 14– kuni, 21 – kuni va 12 oydan so’ng. Emlangandan keyin hosil bo’lgan immunitet 5 yilgacha organizmni himoyalaydi.

Xulosa: O’zbekistonda 2000 – yildan boshlab emlash boshlangan. Bu esa bolalar orasida kasallik tarqalishi 4-5 barobarga kamaydi. Bundan tashqari giyohvandlik, alkogolizm va gomoseksualizm kabi zararli odatlarni kamaytirish, aholi orasida shaxsiy gigiyena chora tadbirlarini tadbiiq qilish va tibbiy xizmat ko’rsatish markazlarida sanitariya qoidalariga rioya qilish kasallikni yanada kamayishiga yordam beradi

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